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Data management plan (DMP)

**Analysis of correlation between
water pollution in Höfen and
Covid-19 cases in Austria, in 2020**

EOSCSecretariat.eu

Version	Effective date	Description of document/changes
1.0	19/04/2023	First version of DMP – created for start of project
2.0	01/05/2023	Second version of DMP – prepared for midterm review

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Introduction

Science Europe practical guide, FAIR data

A DMP is a structured document that keeps record of what research data is created and what happens to that data during and after a project. It helps with planning the research process and defining responsibilities in a research project involving several researchers or institutions.

For writing this DMP, we followed [the recommendations of Science Europe](#) as they reflect the guidelines agreed upon by the major funders in Europe.

To make our data FAIR, they generally will be treated according to the following criteria:

- We will make our data findable, by uploading it to a data repository that provides a persistent identifier, and adding relevant metadata.
- We will make our data accessible by providing open access to data, wherever possible. In cases, where open access is not possible, we will provide meaningful metadata plus contact information for access requests.
- We will make our data interoperable by providing and describing data in a way that is common within our domain by using the same file formats, schemas and vocabularies. We will provide good documentation for all our datasets.
- We will make our data reusable by adding metadata and comprehensive Readme files to all published datasets. The descriptions include details on the methodology used, analytical and procedural information. In case of publication, licenses for code and data will always be assigned and clearly marked.

Relevant Policies and Guidelines

- TU Wien Policy for Research Data Management:
<https://www.tuwien.at/index.php?eID=dms&s=4&path=Directives%20and%20Regulations%20of%20the%20Rectorate/Policy%20for%20Research%20Data%20Management.pdf>
- TU Wien Code of Conduct - Rules to Ensure Good Scientific Practice:
<https://www.tuwien.at/index.php?eID=dms&s=4&path=Directives%20and%20Regulations%20of%20the%20Rectorate/Code%20of%20Conduct%20%E2%80%93%20Rules%20to%20Ensure%20Good%20Scientific%20Practice.pdf>
- Directives and Regulations of the TU Wien Rectorate:
<https://www.tuwien.at/en/tu-wien/organisation/central-divisions/data-protection-and-document-management/directives-regulations/>
- TU Wien Data Protection:
<https://www.tuwien.at/en/tu-wien/organisation/central-divisions/data-protection-and-document-management/data-protection-at-tu-wien>
- European Commission's document on Ethics and Data Protection:
https://ec.europa.eu/info/sites/info/files/5_h2020_ethics_and_data_protection.pdf
- Other (e.g. from a project partner)

1. Data description

1a Lists of datasets that will be reused or produced

Produced datasets

dataset ID	title	type	format	estimated volume	contains sensitive data
P1	research_data_water_pollution_covid.csv	Structured text	.csv	100 MB	no

Reused datasets

dataset ID	title	PID (e.g. DOI) or source	rights (e.g. license)	contains sensitive data
R1	precipitationdata.csv	10.48436/b0g4h-rv840	CC BY-NC-SA 4.0	no
R2	data.csv	https://www.ecdc.europa.eu/en/publications-data/data-daily-new-cases-covid-19-eueea-country	CC BY 4.0	no

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1b Data generation and reuse

Methods and software used for data generation and reuse

The research data is being generated by a Python script, called `water_pollution_covid.py` using the data of water pollution and COVID-19 cases. The data is being processed with `matplotlib`, `numpy`, `csv` and `pandas` libraries. The output file is being generated in `.csv` format, which corresponds to 3 stars in the 5 Star Model.

Two datasets are being reused:

- `precipitationdata.csv` (Concentrations of major ions in wet precipitation samples in Austria)
- `data.csv` (Data on the daily number of new reported COVID-19 cases and deaths by EU/EEA country)

1. Documentation and data quality

2a Data organisation, metadata and documentation

The respective work package leader will handle the structure and versioning of the research data.

As there are no domain specific metadata standards applicable, we will provide a README file with an explanation of all values and terms used at project level. This will help others to identify, discover and reuse our data.

Additionally, we will provide common metadata such as title, description or keywords when publishing data in open access repositories. In such a case, we will follow the default template provided by the repository, such as Data Cite Metadata or Dublin Core.

As far as possible, we will use controlled vocabularies for our data to allow interdisciplinary interoperability and machine-actionability.

A DOI is assigned to the project, which includes all the files used.

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.7930625

URL: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7930625>

2b Data quality control

The following data quality checks will be done: standardised data capture.

2. Storage and backup during research process

3a Storage and backup facilities

For the duration of the project, storage and backup of data will be ensured by the project manager in cooperation with the responsible representative of TU.it. The infrastructure of TU Wien will be used for this purpose.

P1 (research_data.csv), R1 (Concentrations of major ions in wet precipitation samples in Austria), R2 (data.csv) will be stored in TUfiles: TUfiles is a central and

readily available network drive with daily backups and regular snapshots provided by TU.it. It is suitable for storing data with moderate access requirements, but high availability demands that allows full control of allocating authorisations. Only authorized staff members will have access.

3b Data security and protection of sensitive data

We pay strict attention to compliance with the relevant institutional and national data protection policies listed in the introduction of this document. At this stage, it is not foreseen to process any sensitive data in the project. If this changes, advice will be sought from the data protection specialist at TU Wien (Verena Dolovai), and the DMP will be updated.

Access to data during research:

dataset ID	selected project members	all other project members	the public
P1	writing	writing	reading only
R1	reading only	reading only	reading only
R2	writing	writing	reading only

All incidents will be handled individually by an incident response team that is maintaining the affected service.

3. Legal and ethical requirements

4a Personal data

At this stage, it is not foreseen to process any personal data in the project. If this changes, advice will be sought from the data protection specialist at TU Wien (Verena Dolovai), and the DMP will be updated.

4b Intellectual property rights and ownership

There are no legal restrictions on the processing and disclosure of our data.

4c Ethical issues

No particular ethical issue is foreseen with the data to be used or produced by the project. This section will be updated if issues arise.

4. Data sharing and long-term preservation

5a Data publication and access conditions

As far as possible, obtained datasets will be published in repositories. Details on access conditions, reuse licenses, reasons for restrictions, etc. are collected in the table below.

dataset ID	access conditions	restrictions / embargo reasons	estimated publication date	location for publication (repository)	PID	license
P1	Open	2023-05-14	2023-05-12	TU Wien Research Data		CC0 1.0

The repositories used in this project are described in the following paragraph:

TU Wien Research Data is an institutional repository of TU Wien to enable storing, sharing and publishing of digital objects, in particular research data. It facilitates the funders' requirements for open access to research data and the FAIR principles by making research output findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable. This service is developed by the TU Wien Center for Research Data Management and hosted by TU.it. <https://researchdata.tuwien.at/>

Methods or software needed to access and use data: Potential users are required to use Python 3.6+ to run the source code. CSV files can be opened in any program, but highly recommended to use a spreadsheet program, like Microsoft Excel, OpenOffice Calc, or Google Docs. CSV files can be also opened using an online spreadsheet.

5b Long-term preservation and deletion of data

dataset ID	location for long-term storage	minimum retention period (≥ 10 years)	foreseeable research uses and/or users
P1	TU Wien Research Data	10 years	Students and general public

Overview of (unpublished) data that will be deleted:

dataset ID	kind/name of data	date of deletion	reason for deletion	responsible person

5. RDM responsibilities and resources

6a RDM-roles and responsibilities

The [PI / data officer XY] will direct the data management process overall, with the research assistants responsible for ensuring metadata production, day-to-day cross-checks, back-up and other quality control activities are maintained. The lead country researchers will be responsible for routine supervision of the dataset development.

6b Resources

There are no costs dedicated to data management and ensuring that data will be FAIR.

Cost name	Cost type	Description	Unit	Value
Estimated total costs				0

Additional description (if required):